

Improvised Instructional Materials and Academic Achievement in Chemistry: Teacher-Student Perspectives and Measured Impact

Nsikak Stephen Edet (Ph.D)¹; Asian Uko Johnson (Ph.D)² & Precious Nsikak Stephen³

¹Department of Political Science, University of Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

²Department of Public Administration, University of Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

³Department of Chemistry, Akwa Ibom State University,
¹nsikakstephene@yahoo.com, 08069212110, 08082401260

²asianicworld1@gmail.com, 07017754060

³preciousthen2017@gmail.com , 09020379653

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17851561>

Citation: Edet, N. S., Johnson, A. U., & Stephen, P. N. (2025). Improvised Instructional Materials and Academic Achievement in Chemistry: Teacher-Student Perspectives and Measured Impact. *Global Journal of Modern Research and Emerging Trends*, 1(7).

Abstract

This study investigated the use of improvised instructional materials and their influence on academic performance among senior secondary school chemistry students in Government Secondary School, Afaha Atai, Eket. Using a mixed-method sequential exploratory design, data were collected through tests, questionnaires, and focused group interviews from 136 students and 6 chemistry teachers. The study pursued two key objectives: to explore the views of teachers and students regarding the extent to which improvised instructional materials affect academic performance in chemistry and to assess the impact of improvised instructional materials on student achievement. The results showed that both teachers and students strongly believe that improvised materials help with understanding, engagement, and memory. Challenges such as limited funding, lack of improvisation skills, and inadequate motivation were also identified as limiting effective improvisation. Statistical analysis using a dependent t-test showed a significant improvement in students' academic performance following exposure to improvised instructional

materials ($p < 0.05$; Cohen's $d = 0.9$). The study concludes that improvised instructional materials significantly improve student achievement in chemistry and recommends capacity-building for teachers to enhance improvisational pedagogy.

Keywords: improvised instructional materials; academic performance; secondary school students

1.1 Introduction

Chemistry is one of the core science subjects offered at the senior secondary school level in Nigeria. It serves as a foundational requirement for several science-based professional disciplines, including medicine, agriculture, pharmacy, nursing, and biotechnology (Ahmed, 2021). In contemporary Nigeria, national development aspirations place significant emphasis on science and technology, making effective teaching and learning of chemistry central to educational progress. Despite its importance, persistent reports of poor student performance in chemistry examinations across secondary schools in Nigeria continue to be a major concern for educators, policymakers, and parents (Emana, 2020).

The National Policy on Education (GES, 2007) highlights the necessity of practical, exploratory, and experimental approaches to the teaching of science subjects. This philosophy emphasizes the essential function of instructional materials in promoting effective learning. Opoku Asare (2014) emphasized that instructional materials are indispensable tools for engaging learners and supporting the development of scientific process skills. Research evidence consistently shows that the use of well-designed instructional materials significantly improves understanding and academic performance in chemistry (Godswill, Amefiok & Atta, 2015; Flora, 2013). Without these materials, chemistry lessons tend to be overly abstract, teacher-centered, and less effective (Ekanem, 2019).

Unfortunately, many secondary schools in Nigeria face persistent shortages of adequate instructional materials. Azure (2018) reports that most schools lack essential resources needed for effective chemistry instruction. Similarly, Ibitoye and Fabian (2021) identified several factors contributing to poor chemistry performance, including the unavailability of teaching materials, overcrowded classrooms, inadequate laboratory facilities, and insufficiently trained teachers. Udofia (2014) further noted that the poor

state of science laboratories and inadequate resources hinder students' ability to acquire practical skills and achieve proficiency in chemistry.

Given these limitations, many chemistry teachers rely heavily on verbal explanations, which do not foster scientific inquiry, objectivity, critical thinking, or hands-on skills development (Emana, 2020). Nevertheless, the chemistry curriculum advocates activity-oriented and learner-centered teaching approaches that require meaningful interaction between teachers, students, and instructional resources (Akan & Nwosu, 2020). The continued scarcity of essential materials has therefore created a significant instructional gap.

In response to these challenges, improvised instructional materials (locally sourced, low-cost, teacher-constructed teaching aids) have emerged as viable alternatives to standardized resources. Evidence indicates that improvised materials enhance students' engagement, deepen conceptual understanding, and improve academic achievement, especially in resource-constrained environments. They make learning more concrete, meaningful, and relatable by utilizing familiar and readily available local resources.

Despite their potential, the extent to which improvised instructional materials are used in chemistry classrooms and their actual impact on student academic performance remain underexplored in many Nigerian school settings. Therefore, we must investigate how teachers and students perceive these materials and empirically determine their effectiveness in enhancing learning outcomes.

This study is conducted in Government Secondary School, Afaha Atai, Eket, Akwa Ibom State, where shortages of conventional instructional materials present a significant instructional challenge. The research seeks to fill the existing knowledge gap by examining the educational value of improvised materials in chemistry classrooms within this context.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Despite the growing emphasis on science education in Nigeria, student performance in chemistry at the senior secondary level continues to be discouraging. Many learners struggle to understand and retain biological concepts due to the abstract nature of the subject and the persistent reliance on teacher-centered methods. The effective teaching of chemistry requires instructional materials that make ideas concrete, observable, and

relatable. However, most secondary schools in Nigeria, including those in the Eket Local Government Area, experience chronic shortages of standard instructional materials and laboratory resources.

In the absence of adequate resources, teachers often resort to improvised instructional materials constructed from local, low-cost objects. Although improvisation has the potential to enhance engagement, stimulate curiosity, and facilitate more profound understanding, its actual influence on students' academic performance in chemistry has not been sufficiently investigated, especially within resource-limited school environments. Moreover, while teachers and students interact with improvised instructional materials in various ways, little is known about their perceptions regarding the extent to which such materials support learning.

This lack of empirical evidence creates a gap in understanding both the perceived value and the actual academic impact of improvised instructional materials in chemistry instruction. As a result, teachers may remain uncertain about how to best integrate improvisation into their teaching, and policymakers lack the evidence needed to support its systematic use in schools.

Therefore, this study seeks to investigate the issue by (1) exploring teachers' and students' views on how improvised instructional materials influence academic performance in chemistry, and (2) empirically assessing the impact of these materials on students' achievement. The findings are expected to guide practical decision-making aimed at improving chemistry teaching and learning in resource-constrained contexts, such as government secondary schools, Afaha Atai, and Eket.

1.3 Purpose of the Study

This study aims to determine both the perceived and the measurable effects of improvised instructional materials on Chemistry learning outcomes in Government Secondary School, Afaha Atai, Eket. Specifically, it aims to:

- i. Explore the views of teachers and students about the extent to which improvised instructional materials affect students' academic performance in Chemistry.
- ii. Assess the impact of improvised instructional materials on student achievement in Chemistry.

1.4 Significance of the Study

This study holds significance in several important ways. Firstly, it contributes to knowledge by providing empirical evidence on both the perceptions and actual effects of improvised instructional materials on chemistry achievement, thereby enriching the existing body of research on the topic.

Secondly, the findings of this study will offer valuable guidance to chemistry teachers on how to effectively integrate improvised instructional materials into their teaching practices, ultimately enhancing student understanding and performance in the subject.

Thirdly, the study holds policy implications. Educational managers and policymakers can utilize the findings to make informed decisions regarding resource provision, teacher support, and professional development, particularly in schools where adequate instructional materials are lacking.

Finally, the study promotes innovative, low-cost strategies by highlighting practical and resourceful ways in which teachers can use locally available materials to improve learning outcomes, particularly in resource-constrained environments.

1.5 Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the views of teachers and students on the extent to which improvised instructional materials affect students' academic performance in Chemistry?
2. What is the impact of improvised instructional materials on students' academic performance in Chemistry?

Literature Review

2.1 Conceptual Review

Instructional resources play a central role in the effective teaching and learning of chemistry. When appropriately utilized, these resources make learning concrete, real, and meaningful, thereby enhancing students' ability to comprehend and retain complex biological ideas (Ekop, 2019). Students' interaction with instructional materials fosters the development of scientific process skills, self-reliance, and inquiry; these are skills that are essential for national development and scientific literacy. Despite their importance, numerous researchers (Ekop, 2019; Bassey, 2018; Pascal, 2018) report that standard instructional materials remain grossly inadequate in many Nigerian secondary schools.

Given this shortage, chemistry teachers are expected not only to utilize available materials but also to improvise where conventional resources are lacking. The chemistry teacher therefore becomes the central figure in resource utilization and the improvisation of teaching aids. A teacher's willingness and ability to improvise depend on their pedagogical knowledge, content expertise, creativity, and motivation. Where teachers are committed and competent, improvised instructional materials can significantly reduce abstractness, stimulate learners' interest, and support meaningful engagement with scientific concepts, all of which influence academic performance.

2.1.1 Teaching and Learning Chemistry

Chemistry, as a discipline, imparts scientific inquiry skills and provides the cognitive foundation needed for understanding health, agriculture, the environment, and biotechnology. Its teaching aims to foster scientific literacy and prepare learners for higher scientific training and science-related careers (CRDD, 2010). Because chemistry contains numerous abstract concepts, such as cell structure, osmosis, genetics, and ecological interactions, practical activities and visual representations are essential for promoting learning.

However, the success of practical work depends heavily on the availability and effective utilization of instructional materials. While the provision of standard laboratory equipment is important, additional factors, such as teacher training, material suitability, equipment maintenance, and access to consumables, determine the quality of learning experiences (Bassegy, 2018). Effective use of instructional materials stimulates learners' senses, sustains attention, and facilitates deeper comprehension (Denyer, 2018). Unfortunately, due to inadequate funding, poor supply systems, and logistical constraints, many chemistry teachers in developing countries struggle to access the required teaching equipment (Eshiet, 2018).

This situation compels teachers to seek alternative strategies, including the improvisation of instructional materials. Improvisation becomes particularly important when students perceive chemistry as abstract or difficult, leading to low interest and poor performance (Ekanem, 2019). Research findings indicate that the use of instructional materials, including improvised ones, arouses interest, increases retention, and enhances students' participation and performance (Flora, 2019; Kamaifiok, 2020). Without such materials, instructional delivery becomes highly theoretical, making it difficult for learners to internalize biological concepts or connect them to real-life experiences.

Improvised instructional materials therefore become essential tools for engaging learners, supporting differentiated instruction, and creating more meaningful chemistry learning experiences. Their use directly relates to the objectives of this study: understanding teacher and student views about these materials and determining their impact on academic achievement.

2.1.2 Concept of Improvised Instructional Materials

Improvised instructional materials refer to teaching aids developed from locally available, low-cost resources when standard or commercially produced materials are unavailable. According to Bassey in Emanah (2021), improvisation involves the use of imitation or substitute equipment in place of standard ones. Kamoru and Umeono (2020) define improvisation as the inventive utilization of locally sourced materials chosen by the educator to augment instruction. This process requires innovation, flexibility, and a strong understanding of the instructional needs of learners.

Improvised materials may include models, charts, specimens, or equipment constructed from everyday objects such as cardboard, bottles, clay, wood, or plastic. The goal is not merely substitution but the creation of functional tools that support learning. Judy (2014) emphasizes that such materials encourage exploration, independence, and interaction; these are essential components of cognitive and social development.

In chemistry teaching, improvised materials help simplify abstract concepts, provide hands-on learning opportunities, and bridge the gap between theory and practice. They encourage teachers to be resourceful and students to be active participants in constructing knowledge. This aligns directly with the first purpose of the study, exploring how teachers and students perceive improvised instructional materials, and with the second purpose, assessing their effect on academic performance.

Given shortages of standard laboratory equipment in Nigerian secondary schools, improvisation becomes not just an option but a pedagogical necessity. Effective improvisation ensures that resource constraints do not hinder student learning, thereby offering a practical pathway to improving chemistry achievement.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

This study draws on two key educational theories to examine how instructional materials, particularly improvised ones, influence learning outcomes. These are Gagné's Instructional Materials Theory and Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory, which

together provide a robust framework for understanding teachers' and students' perspectives on improvised instructional materials and the impact of these materials on students' academic achievement in chemistry.

Gagné's theory emphasizes a direct link between instructional materials and learning outcomes. It suggests that instructional materials support learning by enhancing cognitive processes, promoting active engagement, clarifying abstract concepts, and strengthening problem-solving abilities. This theory posits that instructional materials guide learners through a sequence of information, demonstrate rules and principles step-by-step, and offer feedback that enhances performance. In the context of chemistry, where concepts can be abstract and complex, these materials help students visualize processes, compare ideas, and apply knowledge to new situations. For this study, Gagné's theory is central because it supports the notion that improvised instructional materials, when used effectively, can improve comprehension and academic performance. It also offers a framework for understanding teacher and student perceptions, underlining the role of instructional materials in shaping learning experiences. However, Gagné's theory does not fully address how learners internalize cultural tools or how social interaction enhances cognition, an aspect more thoroughly explored by Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory.

Vygotsky's sociocultural theory asserts that learning occurs through social interaction and the use of cultural tools, such as instructional resources. These tools mediate thinking by helping learners connect new information with prior experiences, supporting cognitive development, promoting collaboration, and enabling learners to reach higher levels of reasoning. Vygotsky contends that instructional materials actively shape mental functioning. In a chemistry classroom, improvised models or representations allow students to explore, manipulate, and interpret biological structures and processes, thereby developing advanced cognitive skills. This theory aligns with the study's first objective by explaining how teachers and students perceive improvised materials as mediators of learning and with the second objective by showing how these materials may significantly affect academic performance.

Both Gagné's and Vygotsky's theories share the assumption that learning is most effective when students actively engage with materials, ask questions, and construct meaning. Approaches such as question-and-answer, peer instruction, and collaborative learning are grounded in the belief that interacting with tools, especially improvised materials, enhances retention, promotes critical thinking, and improves academic

achievement. On the other hand, teacher-centered approaches, such as traditional lectures, although they provide structure, often lack the engagement necessary for a deep understanding of chemistry concepts. This emphasizes the significance of improvisation in cultivating more interactive and efficacious learning environments, which are the central focus of this study.

The study's aims directly connect to the two theories. Gagné's theory highlights that the quality and availability of instructional materials influence perceptions of learning effectiveness. Vygotsky's theory explains why teachers and students may value improvised materials, as these materials mediate understanding, make learning social, and support cognitive development. Together, these theories justify exploring how teachers and students perceive the usefulness of improvised instructional materials in chemistry classrooms. Additionally, both theories suggest that instructional materials, particularly improvised ones, can enhance learning outcomes. Gagné's theory shows how such materials simplify complex ideas and guide cognitive processes, while Vygotsky's theory demonstrates how interaction with these materials can promote higher-order thinking and improve achievement. Therefore, the use of improvised instructional materials is expected to lead to measurable improvements in students' academic performance, which aligns with the study's second research objective.

2.3 Review of Empirical Studies

2.3.1 Empirical Studies on the Influence of Instructional and Improvised Materials on Students' Academic Performance

Several empirical studies have demonstrated that instructional materials (including improvised ones) play a critical role in enhancing students' learning outcomes. Adeogun (2020) reported a strong positive relationship between the availability of instructional resources and academic achievement. Schools equipped with adequate instructional materials consistently achieved higher performance levels than those with limited resources. This aligns with findings by Babayomi (2019), who argued that the superior academic performance observed in many private schools was linked to the adequacy of teaching and learning resources.

Similarly, Fuller and Clark (2014) emphasized that the quality of instructional materials shapes the quality of learning experiences. According to their study, learners exposed to rich instructional resources develop more profound understanding and improved mastery of concepts. Udosen (2018) further noted that both the quality and quantity of

instructional materials significantly influence student performance, suggesting that chemistry students who have access to charts, models, specimens, real objects, and improvised materials stand a better chance of attaining higher academic outcomes.

Eshiet (2019), in a study conducted in Nigerian primary schools, found that the adequacy of instructional materials directly contributed to learners' improved performance. Although Eshiet focused primarily on physical facilities, his work demonstrates that instructional resources of any form (standard or improvised) are essential for meaningful learning.

Furthermore, Maundu (2017) established that schools with sufficient instructional materials, including locally improvised ones, record consistently higher achievement rates than poorly equipped schools. This reinforces the argument that improvised instructional materials can serve as effective substitutes in resource-constrained environments.

Overall, the reviewed studies show a clear empirical pattern: instructional materials significantly improve student academic achievement, thereby supporting the second purpose of this study.

2.3.2 Empirical Studies on Teachers' and Students' Views Regarding Improved Instructional Materials

Research has shown that teachers' and students' perceptions play a significant role in determining how instructional materials, particularly improvised ones, are used and valued. Several studies highlight recurring challenges teachers face when attempting to utilize or improvise materials, which in turn shape their attitudes.

Godswill, Amefiok, and Atta (2019) noted that many teachers view improvisation positively but are constrained by inadequate funding, especially in rural and public schools. Opoku et al. (2019) found that teachers often express concern that capitation grants and school funding are insufficient to provide even basic materials, leaving improvisation as the only viable option. However, inadequate support from government and local communities weakens teachers' morale and limits innovation.

Another dimension of perception relates to teachers' exposure and competence. Udofia (2018) reported that many teachers acknowledge the usefulness of improvised materials

but feel inadequately trained to produce or use them effectively. This affects their willingness to improvise despite understanding its benefits. Obasi (2018) also found that teachers in rural areas tend to rely heavily on traditional chalkboard methods due to limited exposure to modern instructional technologies that could support improvisation.

From the student perspective, studies such as Nyakno (2018) indicate that learners generally find improvised materials engaging and helpful for understanding complex concepts. Students reported that improvised diagrams, models, and physical objects made lessons more relatable and easier to grasp.

Collectively, these studies reveal a dual narrative:

- i. Teachers appreciate the value of improvised materials but face constraints such as inadequate funding, limited training, and lack of technological support.
- ii. Students view improvised materials as beneficial and performance-enhancing, particularly in chemistry, where abstract concepts require visualization.

These findings directly support the first purpose of the present study.

2.3.3 Empirical Studies on the Impact of Improvised Instructional Materials

A growing body of research shows that improvised teaching materials can make up for a lack of standard teaching materials. Warren, Ogonowski, and Salinger (2020) found that improvisation enhances student engagement, deepens conceptual understanding, and promotes active learning. Their study demonstrated that improvised materials, when carefully planned, offer unique opportunities for hands-on, inquiry-based learning.

Eshiet (2016) stressed that improvisation gives teachers more resources to work with, filling in the gaps that limited funding can leave. His research indicated that improvised materials enable learners to interact with content directly, thereby improving comprehension and retention.

Similarly, Aboderlaheem and Al-Rabane (2015) and Ibe-Basse (2012) concluded that improvised instructional media significantly enhance learning outcomes by utilizing low-cost, contextually relevant materials. Their studies revealed that improvised materials help in simplifying abstract scientific concepts, promoting critical thinking, and improving students' ability to apply knowledge.

Technology-based improvisation has also been shown to enhance learning outcomes. Dodge (2017) found that simple simulations and digital representations (often improvised due to lack of school-provided equipment) improve learners' motivation and performance. UNESCO (2014) likewise documented that ICT-supported improvisation provides access to diverse resources that would otherwise be unavailable, improving the quality of science teaching.

Collectively, these studies reinforce the evidence that improvised instructional materials have a positive and measurable impact on student achievement, directly supporting the second purpose of the study.

The empirical literature reviewed demonstrates two critical insights: Teachers' and students' views reflect both the value and challenges of using improvised instructional materials. Teachers generally acknowledge their usefulness but face limitations such as inadequate funding, lack of training, and poor access to instructional technologies. Students, on the other hand, perceive improvised materials as engaging and helpful for understanding complex chemistry concepts.

Improvised instructional materials significantly influence students' academic achievement. Studies consistently reveal that improvised materials improve engagement, comprehension, critical thinking, and test performance, especially in resource-constrained schools.

These empirical findings substantiate the two major purposes of this study and justify the need to investigate teacher and student perceptions and the impact of improvised instructional materials on chemistry achievement.

3.1 Research Methodology

The research methodology adopted in this study focuses on examining the impact of improvised instructional materials on the academic performance of chemistry students at Government Secondary School, Afaha Atai, located in Eket Local Government Area. The study employs a mixed-method sequential exploratory design, which includes two phases of data collection. The initial phase involves quantitative data collection and analysis, followed by qualitative data collection. This design allows for a comprehensive understanding of the effects of improvised materials, as it combines numerical data with in-depth insights from the participants.

The study is conducted in Government Secondary School, Afaha Atai, which was established in 2020 and has a diverse student body of 1,061 students. The researcher chose this school due to personal familiarity with the area and its heterogeneous population, which provides a range of perspectives. The target population comprises 476 chemistry students and 10 chemistry teachers, with a sample of 152 participants selected using purposive sampling. The participants include students from senior secondary classes and teachers with experience in improvising chemistry materials. The study utilizes tests, questionnaires, and interviews to collect data, with the questionnaires designed to assess the views of both students and teachers on the use of improvised instructional materials and their impact on student performance.

Data analysis is performed using both quantitative and qualitative methods. Quantitative data is organized into frequency tables and analyzed using SPSS software, while qualitative data from interviews is analyzed thematically. The study ensures the validity and reliability of the instruments through expert reviews, pilot testing, and a high reliability coefficient (0.92). Data collection is managed in phases, with questionnaires administered to both students and teachers, followed by focused group interviews with students. The research methodology aims to provide a robust evaluation of the role of improvised instructional materials in improving the academic performance of chemistry students.

4.1 Results and Discussion

4.1.1 Opinions on the Effectiveness of Improvised Instructional Materials for Students' Performance

The researcher aimed to investigate the perspectives of both teachers and students regarding the impact of instructional materials on student performance. The primary focus was to understand why teachers utilize these materials in the teaching process. The findings, presented in Tables 6 and 7 for teachers and students, respectively, reveal insights into this question. When asked whether the instructional materials used by teachers aid students in the learning process, the majority of respondents—63% of teachers (Table 6) and 79% of students (Table 7)—agreed that these materials help improve knowledge and skills. In contrast, a smaller group of 37% of teachers (Table 1) and 21% of students (Table 2) believed the materials primarily help students pass examinations.

These findings align with existing literature, where studies such as Osei-Himah et al. (2018) and Opoku et al. (2019) highlight a strong positive correlation between instructional resources and academic performance. Osei-Himah et al. (2018) suggested that schools with more resources tend to perform better than those with fewer resources, a view supported by the responses from this study. Nyarko and Amevi (2019) also found that private schools outperformed public schools due to the availability and adequacy of teaching and learning resources, further reinforcing the validity of the current findings.

Table 1: Teachers' Views on the Effects of Instructional Materials on Students' Performance

Effect of Instructional Materials	Frequency	Percentage (%)
To Pass Examinations	2	33.33
To Improve Knowledge and Skills	4	67
Total	6	100

Table 2: Students' Views on the Effects of Instructional Materials on their Performance

Effect of Instructional Materials	Frequency	Percentage (%)
To Pass Examinations	28	21
To Improve Knowledge and Skills	108	79
Total	136	100

4.1.2 Impact of Improvised Instructional Materials on Student Achievement in Chemistry

The study sought to determine the impact of improvised instructional materials on student achievement in chemistry. To assess this, a dependent sample t-test was conducted comparing students' performance on pre- and post-intervention tests. The results, shown in Table 3, revealed a significant improvement in student performance. The mean score for the pre-intervention test was 10.57, with a standard deviation of 4.4, indicating a relatively poor understanding of the chemistry concepts being tested. However, after the intervention with improvised instructional materials, the mean score on the post-intervention test increased to 24.76, with a standard deviation of 21.76, reflecting a notable improvement in performance.

The Cohen's d value was calculated at 0.9, which indicates a large effect size, suggesting that the intervention had a substantial positive impact on student learning. A Cohen's d value of 0.9 is considered a forceful effect, typically associated with a significant change in students' abilities. Furthermore, the t-test results showed a statistically significant difference in performance between the pre- and post-intervention tests ($p < 0.05$), confirming that the use of improvised instructional materials led to improved student outcomes. This finding supports the notion that improvised materials can enhance understanding and performance, particularly in complex subjects like chemistry.

The findings of this study align with previous research that underscores the effectiveness of improvised instructional materials in enhancing student learning. By providing a more tangible and engaging way to understand abstract chemistry concepts, these materials can help bridge gaps in students' knowledge. The study's results highlight the importance of integrating innovative, evidence-based teaching strategies in schools to improve educational outcomes, particularly in science education. The significant improvements observed in student performance suggest that using improvised instructional materials could be a valuable tool for enhancing academic achievement in chemistry.

Table 3: Dependent Sample t-Test of Student's Performance on Pre- and Post-Intervention Tests

Statistic	Pre-Intervention Test	Post-Intervention Test	Effect Size
Observation	136	136	---
df	135	---	---
Mean	10.57	24.76	0.9
Standard Deviation (SD)	4.4	21.76	---
P value	0.00		

4.2 Discussion

The findings of this study indicate that the use of improvised instructional materials has a significant positive impact on student performance in chemistry. The pre- and post-intervention test results show a clear improvement in students' understanding of chemistry concepts, with the mean score rising from 10.57 in the pre-intervention test to 24.76 in the post-intervention test. This improvement suggests that the improvised instructional materials played a key role in enhancing students' learning outcomes. The substantial increase in the mean score highlights the potential of these materials to facilitate better understanding, especially in complex subjects like chemistry.

The effect size, calculated using Cohen's *d*, was found to be 0.9, which indicates a large effect. This is a strong indication that the intervention had a considerable impact on student achievement. A Cohen's *d* value of 0.9 is regarded as a significant effect, reinforcing the notion that the improvised materials were highly effective in improving students' performance. The t-test results, which showed a statistically significant difference between the pre- and post-intervention scores ($p < 0.05$), further confirm the positive influence of the instructional materials on student outcomes. The statistically significant results suggest that the observed improvements were not due to chance but rather to the intervention itself.

The large standard deviation observed in the post-intervention scores suggests variability in how the improvised materials impacted individual students. While the overall improvement was substantial, the wide range of responses indicates that some students benefited more from the intervention than others. This could be attributed to differences in prior knowledge, learning styles, or engagement with the materials. However, the overall trend of improvement supports the assertion that improvised

instructional materials are an effective tool for enhancing student performance in chemistry education.

The findings align with previous research that emphasizes the importance of using diverse and engaging instructional materials to enhance student learning. Studies by Osei-Himah et al. (2018) and Opoku et al. (2019) have similarly highlighted a strong positive relationship between instructional resources and academic performance, and this study adds to that body of evidence. The substantial enhancements noted in this study indicate that the integration of additional hands-on, practical learning resources into chemistry education may facilitate the resolution of comprehension deficits and enhance academic achievement.

The results also show how important it is to use evidence-based teaching methods to improve student learning. The use of improvised instructional materials in the classroom offers a cost-effective and innovative solution, particularly in schools with limited access to conventional teaching resources. This study contributes to the growing body of literature advocating for the use of such materials as a means of enhancing science education and suggests that educators should consider integrating improvised resources into their teaching practices to support student achievement.

5.1 Conclusion

This study has demonstrated that the use of improvised instructional materials can significantly enhance the academic performance of chemistry students. The findings revealed that students' performance improved between the pre- and post-intervention tests, with a large effect size of 0.9, indicating a substantial positive impact of the intervention. The results also indicated that the improvised materials helped students not only to pass exams but also to improve their understanding of chemistry concepts. Despite the variation in individual student responses, the overall improvement in performance supports the conclusion that improvised instructional materials are an effective tool in enhancing student learning outcomes, particularly in science subjects.

The results of this study are consistent with previous research that emphasizes the importance of instructional resources in improving academic performance. The positive relationship observed between the use of improvised materials and students' achievement further underscores the need for teachers to explore innovative ways to deliver content, especially in schools with limited access to traditional teaching aids.

This study contributes to the growing body of literature that supports the integration of improvised materials into teaching strategies, offering a viable alternative to expensive or hard-to-access educational resources.

5.2 Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, several recommendations can be made to enhance chemistry education using improvised instructional materials:

- 1. Adoption of Improvised Materials in Schools:** Educators should consider integrating improvised instructional materials into their teaching strategies. Given their positive impact on student performance, these materials offer an effective and low-cost alternative to traditional teaching aids, particularly in resource-constrained environments.
- 2. Teacher Training on Improvised Materials:** Schools should provide training for teachers on how to create and effectively use improvised instructional materials. This will help teachers to develop their skills in designing and implementing materials that are relevant to the curriculum and capable of engaging students.
- 3. Further Research:** Future studies should explore the long-term effects of improvised instructional materials on student achievement. Another study could investigate the factors that contribute to the varying effects of these materials on individual students, such as prior knowledge, learning styles, and engagement levels.
- 4. Encouraging Student Engagement:** Schools should encourage student participation in the creation and use of improvised materials. This could foster a more profound understanding of the subject matter and increase student motivation and engagement in the learning process.
- 5. Policy Support:** Educational policymakers should consider incorporating the use of improvised materials into national education strategies, especially in areas where access to conventional teaching resources is limited. Support for such initiatives could help improve the quality of education, particularly in science subjects.

In conclusion, this study highlights the importance of innovative teaching strategies, such as the use of improvised instructional materials, in improving educational outcomes. By adopting these materials, educators can enhance students' understanding of complex subjects like chemistry, leading to improved academic performance and a more engaging learning experience.

References

- Bassey, P. N. (2018). The nature of science process skills. *Research in Science and Technological Education*, 13(1), 5-11.
- Cohen, L., Manion, L., & Morrison, K. (2018). *Research methods in education* (8th ed.). Routledge.
- Ekanem, C. (2019). Science, Technology and Mathematics Curriculum Development. Focus on Problems and prospects of Chemistry Delivery. In Udofia, N. A. (Ed.), *49th Annual Conference Proceedings of STAN on Science Curriculum development* (77-81). Ibadan: Heinemann.
- Ekanem, C. R. (2018). Enriching Senior Secondary School Chemistry through Integrating Entrepreneurship Activities. *50th Annual Proceedings of Science Teachers' Association of Nigeria (STAN)*, 128-133.
- Emana, J. K. (2020). Rationale and approaches for improvisation in science. *Journal of Education Research*, 1(1), 23-29.
- Flora, J. N. K. (2019). Education Studies for Teachers. *Journal of Science Education*, 1(3), 175-176.
- Gagné, R. M., Wager, W. W., Golas, K. C., & Keller, J. L. (2015). *Principles of instructional design*. Thompson.
- Godswill, E. T., Amefiok, E. T., & Atta, E. T. (2017). *Principles and methods of teaching*. Black Mask Limited.
- Nyarko, A. O., & Amevi, S. K. (2019). An investigation into the availability and extent of resources in the teaching of Chemistry in some Nigerian public and private schools. *European Journal of Education*, 4(1), 290-291.
- Opoku, A. (2018). Meeting the challenge of accessibility and utilization of modern instructional materials in rural senior high schools in Nigeria. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 1(2), 1-13.

- Opoku, A., Annan, P. K., & Agbesi, J. M. (2019). Resource and resource utilization as correlates of school academic performance. *Review of Educational Research*, 4(2), 11-15.
- Osei-Himah, V., Parker, J., & Asare, I. (2018). The effects of improvised materials on the study of science in basic schools in Aowin Municipality – Nigeria. *Research on Humanities and Social Sciences*, 8(8), 20-23.
- Udofia, P. A. O. (2020). *Practical handbook on instructional media* (2nd ed.). Graphcom Publishers, Ilorin.
- Vygotsky, L. S. (1978). *Mind in society: The development of higher psychological processes*. Harvard University Press.